

The Zapotec or Ben 'Zaa (The Cloud People)

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The Zapotecs or Ben 'Zaa are an Indigenous peoples of Mexico that live primarily in the modern state of Oaxaca. They practice a syncretic Catholicism merged with traditional Prehispanic practices and beliefs.

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 2022 CE

Region: Present-day Zapotec-speaking peoples in Oaxaca

Region tags: Mexico

Current extant of where Zapotec-speaking peoples live in the modern Mexican state of Oaxaca. Zapotecs can also live in Mexico City and parts of the west coast of the United States of America, in particular California.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Joyce, Arthur. 2010. *Mixtecs, Zapotecs, and Chatinos: Ancient Peoples of Southern Mexico. The Peoples of America*. Malden, Mass.: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Source 2: Lynn, Stephen. 1996. The Creation and Re-Creation of Ethnicity: Lessons from the Zapotec and Mixtec of Oaxaca. *Latin American Perspectives*, 89(23:2), pps 17-37.
- Source 3: There are many books and articles available on Prehispanic, Colonial, and modern Zapotec culture, language, religion and traditional lifeways.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: .

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: .

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: Practices and beliefs associated with Prehispanic traditions are oral in nature.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Practices and beliefs associated with Prehispanic traditions would have been revealed by a variety of supernatural beings.

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Practices and beliefs associated with Prehispanic traditions were inspired by natural phenomena.

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

Notes: Individuals often have their own interpretations of both official Roman Catholic scripture and Prehispanic traditions.

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– Yes

Notes: Technically only officials of the Roman Catholic Church are allowed to interpret scripture.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the Roman Catholic hierarchy. For Prehispanic traditions, respected elders.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: For Roman Catholics, the Bible.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Protestant groups have been attempting to convert practicing Catholic Zapotecs. The Mormons and Jehovah's Witnesses have been especially active in this regard.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Conversion by Protestant groups have caused tensions in some villages between adherents and their Catholic neighbors.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– I don't know

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Varies depending on the size of the settlement and the number of religious monuments it can support. With respect to Prehispanic traditions, many monuments are natural phenomena that occur outside of the settlement.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 160000

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Temporary religious architecture, natural phenomena, etc.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 95

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– I don't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: State and municipal governments will lend financial support to restore and maintain historic churches.

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– No

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (with smaller religious groups not officially allowed but in practice tolerated)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Prehispanic traditions or Catholic beliefs grafted onto Prehispanic traditions are frequently oriented to environmental features.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader of a local community:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:
 - No
 - ↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):
 - Yes
 - ↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:
 - Number of levels [numeric value]: 5
- ↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:
 - No
- ↳ Are religious leaders chosen:
 - Yes
 - ↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:
 - No
 - ↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:
 - No
 - ↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Yes

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a leader's own followers:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by other leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Charges of fallibility made by a political ruler:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

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Architecture, Geography

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Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: During the Days of the Dead, the spirits are able to return to the living world and communicate with the living. They also eat, drink, and enjoy music.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic God cares about believing in Him alone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: Premartial sex

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
 - Notes: At the same time, everyone gossips.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Field doesn't know

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:
– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present:
– No

Are supernatural beings present:
– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic priests are the representatives of God/Jesus Christ on earth.

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic God is omnipresent and all-knowing.

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Jealousy, callousness

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Mainly through religious specialists, not only.
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No

- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: On Days of the Dead altars, food and drink are often left out for the deceased.

- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Normal range of human emotions

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: Indirectly through signs or signals

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as they are natural phenomena.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as they are natural phenomena

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

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– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: In a metaphysical sense.

- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Normal range of other emotions, capacities for destruction and creation.

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
 - Notes: In the present day no, but in the Preshispanic past for sure.

- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

- Yes

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Heaven and Hell in Roman Catholic Tradition; Mictlan in Prehispanic traditions.

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Heaven usually located above.

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Hell in Roman Catholic tradition usually located below.

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: Mictlan

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Yes

|

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Moral distinctions associated with the Roman Catholic Church and conventional distinctions associated with Indigenous cultural beliefs, some shared across Indigenous groups and some specific to Zapotecs.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Natural disasters visited upon the community

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Can be depending on the beliefs of the individual

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness[]:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

Notes: But it can appear that way.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

- ↳ Cremation:
 - No
- ↳ Mummification:
 - No
- ↳ Interment:
 - Yes
- ↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):
 - No
- ↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):
 - Yes
- ↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):
 - No
- ↳ Corpse is interred some other way:
 - No
- ↳ Cannibalism:
 - No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: During the Days of the Dead, the spirits are able to return to the living world and communicate with the living. They also eat, drink, and enjoy music.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven and Hell in Roman Catholic Tradition; Mictlan in Prehispanic traditions.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Notes: Heaven usually located above.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

Notes: Hell in Roman Catholic tradition usually located below.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Mictlan

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic priests are the representatives of God/Jesus Christ on earth.

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic God is omnipresent and all-knowing.

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Jealousy, callousness
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Mainly through religious specialists, not only.
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
 - ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– No

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: On Days of the Dead altars, food and drink are often left out for the deceased.

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Normal range of human emotions

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Indirectly through signs or signals

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as they are natural phenomena.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Inasmuch as they are natural phenomena

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In a metaphysical sense.
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Normal range of other emotions, capacities for destruction and creation.
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: In the present day no, but in the Preshispanic past for sure.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Roman Catholic God cares about believing in Him alone.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: Premartial sex

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: At the same time, everyone gossips.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
 - Yes
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
 - Yes

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Natural disasters visited upon the community

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Can be depending on the beliefs of the individual

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– I don't know

Notes: But it can appear that way.

- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

- No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

- Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

- Present and clear

Notes: Moral distinctions associated with the Roman Catholic Church and conventional distinctions associated with Indigenous cultural beliefs, some shared across Indigenous groups and some specific to Zapotecs.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

- Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

- Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

- Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

- No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):
– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):
– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Monogamy (females):
– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:
– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: But only after church services and during certain parts of the ritual performances. Not requirements of the rituals themselves.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: But only after church services and during certain parts of the ritual performances. Not requirements of the rituals themselves.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Indigenous peoples living in a modern nation state with varying degrees of participation in that state.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic church.

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithes

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: During the Prehispanic era there was a Zapotec script.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government programs

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic church

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government programs

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic Church

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government programs

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Indigenous peoples living in a modern nation state with varying degrees of participation in that state.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic church.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Government programs

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic church

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government programs

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Catholic Church

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through government programs

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: Tithes

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: During the Prehispanic era there was a Zapotec script.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

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